

Supporting Information for

In-situ silt generation in the Taklimakan Desert evidenced by uranium isotopes

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Introduction

This Supporting Information includes discussions of the influences from the initial ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) ratio, (Text A1 and Figure S1), and mass balance calculation and a report of measured U concentration (Text A2).

Text A1: Influence of the initial ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) ratio

Here we have done two analyses to demonstrate the >1 values have limited influence on our findings:

1) We conduct a sensitivity analysis to evaluate how the calculated mass contributions from the *in-situ* processes change as a function of the initial ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) ratio, and our results (Figure S1) show that the estimated mixing fraction from desert processes is relatively insensitive to the ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) of the fresh end-member;

Figure S1. Illustration showing the sensitivity of the contribution fraction of desert processes to the initial ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) ratio

2) we demonstrate that changes in the initial ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) would not influence the difference between the comminution ages among samples through the mathematical derivations below:

The evolution of the ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) with time is described by the following equation (DePaolo et al., 2006):

$$A_{meas} = (1 - f) + [A_0 - (1 - f)]e^{-\lambda T_{com}} \quad (\text{Eq. S1})$$

where A_{meas} is the measured ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) of the silt-sized particles, f is the recoil factor of ^{238}U , A_0 represents the initial activity ratio, λ is the decay constant of ^{234}U , and T_{com} is the comminution age.

Rearranging Eq. S1 yields this expression for the comminution age:

$$T_{com} = -\frac{1}{\lambda} \ln \left[\frac{A_{meas} - (1-f)}{A_0 - (1-f)} \right] \quad (\text{Eq. S2})$$

For two samples with different comminution ages (T_1, A_1 and T_2, A_2 , respectively), the difference in their comminution ages can be expressed as:

$$\Delta T = T_1 - T_2 = -\frac{1}{\lambda} \ln \left[\frac{A_1 - (1-f)}{A_2 - (1-f)} \right] \quad (\text{Eq. S3})$$

Eq. S3 that the difference in comminution age among samples is independent of the initial activity ratio, A_0 .

Therefore, the U isotopes can still be used as a tracer to distinguish the silt-sized particles with different comminution ages produced by different processes.

Text 2: Mass balance calculation and measured U concentrations

Here we derive two mathematical demonstrations to analyze the relationship between the contributions to the U element and the contributions to the silt mass in the end-member mixing calculation. First, we show that in two end-member mixing, if two

concentrations in the three concentrations (two end-members and the mixture) are equivalent, all three concentrations are equal. Second, we demonstrate that normalizing the contributions to U by the U concentrations of the end-members returns the contributions to mass.

We consider two end-members (1 and 2) and assign the corresponding U isotopes and concentrations of the two end-members as A_1 , $[U]_1$ and A_2 , $[U]_2$, respectively. following the mass balance of U element, the end-member mixing equations can be expressed:

$$A_{mix} = A_1 \times m + A_2 \times (1 - m) \quad (\text{Eq. S4})$$

Similar to k_{DP-TD} and k_{DP-KSL} in the main text, m is the fraction of U contributed from end-member 1.

The fraction (n) of silt mass of the mixing end-member contributed from end-member 1 can be modeled by mass balances of U concentration and isotopes:

$$[U]_{mix} = [U]_1 \times n + [U]_2 \times (1 - n) \quad (\text{Eq. S5})$$

$$A_{mix}[U]_{mix} = A_1[U]_1 \times n + A_2[U]_2 \times (1 - n) \quad (\text{Eq. S6})$$

According to the Eq. S5 and treating the mixture as a third end-member, if the U concentrations of the two of the three end-members are the same, the U concentration of the other end-member should be the same as that of the remaining two end-members. Under this scenario ($[U]_1 = [U]_2 = [U]_{mix}$), Eq. S6 can be simplified to Eq. S7:

$$A_{mix} = A_1 \times n + A_2 \times (1 - n) \quad (\text{Eq. S7})$$

Combining Eqs S4 and S7, we obtain $m = n$. In other words, if the U concentrations of the end-members 1 and 2 are the same, the contributed fraction of U element (m) equates to the mass contribution to silt (n).

In the case of this study, the two contributing end-members are the silts from the

in-situ processes and mountainous processes, respectively. The U concentration and isotopes of silts produced by the mountainous processes can be represented by the fluvial sediment samples from the eastern Kunlun Shan (reservoir (2)). However, the fresh silts produced by *in-situ* processes in desert are difficult to collect. Note that although the U isotopes of the fresh silts produced by *in-situ* processes can be approximated by the ground particles obtained from laboratory work, it is hard to predict whether there will be fractionation of U concentration across grain size classes, because minerals have the same initial ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) ratio but different U concentrations when they are broken (Bosia et al., 2018). Therefore, the U concentration of silt produced by the *in-situ* processes is more difficult to measure directly compared to the ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) ratio.

Here we constrain the U concentration of the freshly produced TD silts from the *in-situ* processes using the measured U concentrations of the 20-25- μm fractions of the TD and mountainous fluvial sediment samples (mean $\pm 1\sigma$, 3.34 ± 0.20 ppm, $n = 5$, and 3.20 ± 0.37 ppm, $n = 7$, respectively) (Table S3). We conduct the Mann-Whitney U-test and the result ($p = 0.3939$) cannot reject the null hypothesis that the U concentrations of the 20-25- μm fractions of the TD and mountainous fluvial sediment samples are drawn from the same distribution (at 5% confidence). In other words, the U concentrations of the 20-25- μm fractions of the TD and mountainous fluvial sediment samples cannot be distinguished statistically, meaning the U concentrations of silts produced by the *in-situ* processes and mountainous processes should be the same. Hence, in this study, the mass fractions of U element are the same as the material contribution of the silts produced by the *in-situ* processes to TD silts and Kunlun Shan loess, respectively.

References

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